

MODELLING THE PERFORMANCE OF A COGENERATION UNIT CONSUMING SEVERAL FUELS

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Abstract

Pulp and paper mill represent big source of energy rich biomass. The biggest sources of biomass in chemical pulp mills are black liquor which consists of spent cooking chemicals, lignin and hemicellulose and wood residuals. Traditional way of processing this source of energy in pulp mills is combustion in recovery boilers, where the produced steam is used in steam turbines for heat and electric energy cogeneration. However, modern gasification technology which is considered to be more efficient than combustion in term of electric energy production can replace this traditional way. On the other hand, integration of gasification process into the pulp mill will affect another process of the heat and electric energy production, and thus the whole cogeneration unit must be redesigned.

Typical large paper mill with annual production of 1600 tonnes of black liquor dry solids per day and 30 tonnes of wood residuals per hour is considered in our study. Integrated gasification combined cycle based on both types of biomass fuels (black liquor and wood residuals) is compared with traditional cogeneration units in pulp mills in terms of net electric energy production. Also, different ways of connection between these processes will be designed and considered as well as comparison of their performance with that of separate units.

Introduction

Chemical (Kraft) pulp represents up to 70 % of all pulp produced in the Europe¹. An integral part of chemical pulping process is a recovery cycle, where spent cooking chemicals are recovered from the black liquor². Black liquor is a viscous black liquid, the mixture of inorganic salts (such as Na_2CO_3 , NaHS , Na_2SO_4) and organic chemicals removed from pulp (hemicelluloses and lignin). Black liquor represents a huge source of energy rich biomass in pulp mills, up to 7 tonnes of black liquor are produced in the manufacture of 1 tonne of pulp³. Traditional way of processing the black liquor, is its evaporation in series of evaporators and concentrators up to 70 – 85 % of solids, combustion in the recovery boiler, causticizing and the white liquor production^{2,4}. However, black liquor is not the only source of biomass in the pulp mill, such wastes are produced in all stages of pulp productions – wood preparation, paper production, regeneration of chemicals and waste water treatment. If the energy recovery is done from all of these sources, energy demands of pulp mill can reduce by 50 %⁵.

The main sources of biomass in pulp mills are black liquor and wood residuals. As it was already mentioned, this biomass is traditionally combusted in boilers. However, modern technology of gasification can be used to improve the efficiency of the recovery process. In the gasification process, organic chemicals from the biomass are transferred by several chemical reactions into combustible gas⁶. This gas can be then used as a fuel in cogeneration heat and power plant or as a feed to production of some valuable chemicals. There are two main types of gasification technologies – low-temperature (600 – 850 °C) and high-temperature (900 – 1000 °C) gasification^{1,6}. Also, depending on the used oxidizer, there is gasification with using air or pure oxygen. The advantage of low-temperature gasification is better separation of inorganics as solids, however, disadvantages are lower reaction rate and sulphate reduction. In the high-temperature gasification there is lower sulphur reduction and higher reaction rate, but molten inorganics can cause corrosion of the reactor⁶. Depending on the type of oxidizer, the heating value of produced gas can change. With using pure oxygen, lower heating value can be up to 3 times higher than in the system with using air as source of oxygen¹. Even if the gasification process could be a good alternative to combustion process, integration of gasification process would affect other processes of heat and electric energy production, and thus the whole cogeneration unit must be redesigned. This involves huge investment costs, which can make this process not economically feasible.

The aim of this work is to compare traditional technology of biomass (black liquor and wood residuals) combustion with its gasification in term of power production. Also, different ways of connection between these processes will be studied to maximize the power production.

System description

In the first part of the work, combustion process of both, black liquor and wood residuals, has to be modelled. Input for the calculations is 1600 tonnes per day of black liquor dry solids (water content 75 % wt.) and 30 tonnes per hour of wood residuals with the moisture of 20 %. Parameters set for biomass combustion are following:

- Thermal efficiency of steam production from black liquor and wood residuals 75 % and 78 % respectively
- Parameters of produced superheated steam in boilers – 9.5 MPa, 490 °C (black liquor combustion) and 6 MPa, 440 °C (wood residuals combustion)
- Steam from boiler enters the extraction-condensing steam turbine – extractions at 1.2 MPa, 0.6 MPa; condensing pressure 8 kPa (a)
- Deaerator operates at 120 °C

In both cases of the gasification process, the assumed condensate return efficiency from process is 70 % of the exported steam and the deaerator operates at the temperature of 104 °C. The necessary condition for comparing gasification and combustion process and to provide steam need for pulp and paper mill is the amount of produced medium-pressure (MP) and low-pressure (LP) steam in all the studied processes, which has to be the same in all cases. In all studied cases, isentropic expansion efficiency and mechanic efficiency of steam turbines were set to 80 % and 95 % respectively.

For the system with wood residuals gasification (Figure 1), following parameters were set:

- Gasification with air at atmospheric pressure and temperature 900 °C
- Gas leaving the gasifier with the temperature of 290 °C
- Sulphur content in produced gas less than 40 ppm – no need of gas cleaning⁷
- Combustion of gas with the air in combustion chamber (CC) and production of steam in heat recovery steam generator (HRSG)
- Expansion of high-pressure (HP) steam in steam turbine

System with black liquor gasification (Figure 2) includes:

- Gasification with pure oxygen at 950 °C and 3 MPa
- Cooling and cleaning of the gas in series of heat exchangers and absorption column
- Combustion of gas with the air in gas turbine and expansion of flue gases to atmospheric pressure
- Steam production from remaining heat of flue gases in HRSG
- Expansion of produced HP steam in steam turbine

Figure 1. Schematic description of wood residuals gasification system with combined cycle

Figure 2. Schematic description of black liquor gasification. There is a possibility of combustion of gas produced in the wood residuals gasification process (grey line)

Results

In table I, the composition of gases produced by biomass gasification is shown together with lower heating values for each gas. The amount of net produced electric energy and steam in all modelled systems are shown in Table II. According to results in Table II it is clear, that the gasification technology is more effective in term of electric energy production.

Table I
Composition and lower heating value (LHV) of syngas produced by BL and WR gasification

	BL gasification (vol. %)	WR gasification (vol. %)
CO ₂	31.1	20.0
H ₂	35.5	17.5
CO	30.6	10.8
CH ₄	1.6	1.5
H ₂ S	1.15	-
N ₂	-	50.2
LHV (MJ/kg)	8	4.2

Table II
Amounts of produced steam and electric energy in modelled systems of biomass combustion and gasification

	Combustion		Gasification		
	BL	WR	BL	WR	BL + WR
LP steam (kg/s)	21.95	22.66	21.95	22.66	44.61
MP steam (kg/s)	9.41	11.33	9.41	11.33	20.77
El. energy (MW)	37.4	11.7	56.7	17.4	72.0
Comparison (MW)	-	-	+ 19.3	+ 5.7	+ 22.9

With the results shown above, investment costs and payback period of purchasing the gasification system with combined heat and power production instead of boiler can be evaluated. For the set amounts of processed biomass, prices of boilers including steam turbine and auxiliaries was estimated according to Larson⁸ as 112 mil. € for black liquor boiler and 67 mil. € for wood residuals boiler. For the black liquor and wood residuals integrated gasification combined cycle, investment costs were with the help of literature^{8,9} estimated to 191 mil. € and 90 mil. € respectively. The investment costs of black liquor integrated gasification combined cycle with co-firing of gas from wood residuals gasification were estimated as 241 mil. €. Simple payback period for model prices of electric energy, varying between 40 and 100 €/MWh, is shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Simple payback period of black liquor and wood residual integrated gasification combined cycle system purchase compared to the recovery boiler for different prices of electric energy

As shown above, the best variant is to purchase black liquor gasification system connected with the wood residuals gasification system. The shorter payback period (2 – 4 years shorter) is caused by purchasing just one steam turbine and one heat recovery steam generator for processing of two different fuels.

Conclusion

As it is shown in Table II, biomass gasification is more efficient than its combustion in term of electric energy production. Based on these data and investment costs for every modelled system, we were able to estimate the incremental simple payback period if an investment in IGCC system is considered, with an alternative of traditional recovery boiler purchase. By choosing both black liquor and wood residuals IGCC system instead of purchasing boilers, payback period ranges between 5 to 12 years, depending on the price of electric energy. According to the results in Figure 3, the best variant with the shortest payback period is gasification of both biomass sources with co-firing of gas from wood residuals gasification in HRSG with flue gases from black liquor gasification.

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